

Tectonics

Supporting Information for

Provenance of the Mesozoic succession of Franz Josef Land (north-eastern Barents Sea): Paleogeographic and tectonic implications for the High Arctic

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Attachment 1. Stratigraphic column and photos of Location 1 and 2

**Location 1
Wilczek Land**

**Location 2
Hall Island**

- coarse- to medium grained sands and sandstones
- fine-grained sands and sandstones
- clay, argillites
- matrix supported conglomerates
- siltstones
- pebbles and cobbles
- dated samples
- basalts

